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BCMRI: MRI-based Breast Cancer Digital Repository
(Phenotypes Detection and Diagnosis)

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Overview

- I. Background and Motivation
- II. MRI-based Breast Cancer Digital Repository
- III. Detection of Pathological Lesions
- IV. Diagnosis of Breast Cancer Phenotypes
- V. Preliminary Results and Future Work.

Background and Motivation

- Recent studies have demonstrated a moderate to high data correlation between of MRI-based imaging phenotypes of pathological lesions (tumors) and cancer clinics, molecular, genomic related characteristics.
- Machine (Deep) Learning-based models focused on the imaging features have been trained to predict molecular, genomic, and proliferation characteristics of tumors molecular subtypes (i.e., clinical surrogate and clinical endpoints)
- *It has been possible to establish an association between tumor molecular biomarkers and algorithmically assessed quantitative imaging (radiomics) features.*

Motivation

- Biomarkers derived from medical images inform on disease detection, characterization and treatment response.
- Quantitative imaging biomarkers have potential to provide objective decision-support tools in the management pathway of patients.
- *Measurement variability needs to be understood and systems for data acquisition and analysis harmonized before using quantitative imaging measurements to drive clinical decisions.*

Motivation

- BC is the first type of cancer with a higher incidence in women.
- Treatment methods have proven to be very effective in increasing life expectancy with early detection.
- *MRI is increasingly an option and common practice in clinical workflows.*
- *MRI analysis is expensive and time-consuming which demands highly specialized skills.*
- Pattern recognition in images using CNNs achieves increasingly better results.

BREAST CANCER DIGITAL REPOSITORY

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Film **Digital**

→ Select the characteristics desired for the search. Blank form show all the patients in the repository.

Gender ?

Female Male

Segmentations ?

With Segmentations?

Patient ?

Patient Id

Mammography ?

Normal Anomaly

Nodule

Microcalcification

Calcification

Axillary Adenopathy

Architectural Distortion

Stroma Distortion

Age(Value) ?

Value

Age(Interval) ?

Breast Density ?

n/a < 25%

25% to 50% 51% to 75%

> 75%

Breast Location ?

Left Right

QSI QSE

QII QIE

Axillary

Central

Retroareolar

Biopsy Result ?

No

Benign

Suspect

Insufficient / Unrepresentative

Malignant

Definitive Diagnosis ?

No

Benign

C.I.S.

Invasive C.

Micro C.

Others

Undetermined

Classification ?

Unassigned Birads 0

Birads 1 Birads 2

Birads 3 Birads 4A

Birads 4B Birads 4C

Birads 5 Birads 6

[Reset search](#)

Patient 23 Age 74 Female 1 studie(s)									
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◀◀ 1 2 3 4 5 ▶▶

69 patient(s) found - page 1/14

Development and Partners:

 ineqi driving innovation

 U.PORTO

 FMUP FACULDADE DE MEDICINA
UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO

 SAO JOAO

 GOVERNIO DE ESPAÑA

 CENTRO EXTREMEÑO DE
TECNOLOGÍAS AVANZADAS
CETA Ciemat

 universidade
de aveiro

 FCT
Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia

 EUROPEAN UNION
EUROPEAN REGIONAL
DEVELOPMENT FUND

BCDR was released
for public use /
domain on April 18,
2012

(<https://bcdr.eu/>)

MIWAD-DB 1.2 (Utilizador: Dr. Bruno)

Pacientes

Primeiro	Anterior	Seguinte	Último
PIN	Nome	Apelidos	Sexo
hsj009302...			Feminino
hsj009305...			Feminino
hsj009305...			Feminino
hsj009402...			Feminino
hsj009406...			Feminino

Palavra de pesquisa

PIN hsj0094025687 Sexo Feminino

PID hsj000000044 Avaliado: Não

Nome

Nascimento 8/Ago/1917 Idade 94

Novo Guardar Apagar

Estudos

Número	Data estudo	Número de Les...	Avaliado
00010738-J	10/11/1994	3	Não
0000000000	11/03/2004	2	Não

Número 00010738-J

Data estudo 10/Nov/1994

Densidade Moderada involução adiposa

Observações

Ver relatório anterior Novo

Carregar relatório anterior Guardar

Apagar relatório Apagar

Gerar relatório

Lesões | Imagens

Número	Mama	Diagnóstico
1	Esquerda	Não
2	Esquerda	Não
3	Esquerda	Não

Nova Guardar Apagar

Localização mama

Direita Esquerda

QSE QIE

QSI QII

Central Axilar

Retroareolar

Mamografia

Normal Anomalia

Nódulo Alteração da arquitectura

Calcificações Distorção do estroma

Microcalcificações Adenopatias axilares

Segmentações

Série	Tipo	Mama	Utilizador	Data	CAD

Ver na imagem Apagar Mostrar vector

Classificações

Família	Classe	Data	Utilizador

Ecografia

Não Normal Anomalia

Nódulo cístico Ectasias

Nódulo sólido Outros

Microcalcificações

Radiologia

Não Sim

Incidência 1 Incidência 2

Distância 0 Dimensão 0

Características da lesão

Benigna P-Benigna

Maligna P-Maligna

Indeterminada

Localização

Não Sim

Arpão

Carbono

Biopsia Anatomia patológica Post Biopsia Cirurgia Diagnóstico definitivo

BCDR was released for public use / domain on April 18, 2012

(<https://bcdr.eu/>)

BCMRI: A new -on development- **MRI**-based
Breast Cancer Digital Repository

BCMRI: MRI-based BC Digital Repository

- An ongoing scientific collaboration project between of “*Centro Hospitalar de Setúbal*” and “*Instituto Politécnico de Setúbal*”, Portugal.
- Digital content (**MRI-based**, Mammography, Ultrasound, Tomosynthesis)
 - *The MRI scanners used in the study are, in order of frequency:*
 - GE Signa Voyager 1.5T
 - Siemens Magnetom Skyra 3T
 - Philips Multiva 1.5T
 - GE Explorer
 - GE Optima MR450w 1.5T
 - GE Optima MR360w 1.5T

BCMRI: MRI-based BC Digital Repository

➤ MRI associated Metadata.

<p>Location of the lesion: RB: _____ LB: _____</p> <p>Features of the lesion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Focus</i>• <i>Linear</i> <i>non-mass</i> _____ Segmental _____ Regional _____ Multiple Regions _____ Diffuse _____• <i>Mass</i> <i>dimensions</i> _____ morphology oval _____ round _____ irregular _____ margins circumscribed _____ irregular _____ spiculated _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Internal pattern homogeneous _____ heterogeneous _____ ring-shaped _____ with internal septa without enhancement _____• Initial enhancement < 50% _____ 50% a 100% _____ >100% _____• Post initial enhancement in crescendo _____ plateaued _____ washout _____ <p>Grade BI RADS: _____</p>
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BCMRI: MRI-based BC Digital Repository

- All patients had previous diagnostic core-biopsies
- All lesions (cancers) were histologically classified into four groups or subtypes: **Luminal A, Luminal B, HER2 enriched and triple negative tumors** according to the status of estrogen receptors, progesterone receptors, HER2 receptors and Ki67 receptors detected by immunohistochemistry (IHC) on the surface of cell membranes.

BCMRI: MRI-based BC Digital Repository

- BC tumors are classified according to the following criteria:
 - **Luminal A** (*ER-and/or PR-positive/HER2-negative/low Ki-67*),
 - **Luminal B** (*ER- and/or PR-positive/HER2-negative/high Ki-67*),
 - **HER2-enriched** (*overexpression of HER2 regardless of the expression of other markers*),
 - **Triple negative** (*ER and PR absent/HER2-negative*).

ER/PR expression is defined as positive if it stains in >1% of total tumor cell nuclei. As for HER2: + negative, ++ uncertain and +++ positive.

Cancers with HER-2 scores 2+ should be evaluated further by fluorescent in situ hybridization (SISH or FISH).

Low Ki67 is defined by less than or equal to 20% cell count per field ($\leq 20\%$), while high Ki67 is defined by Ki67 cell count above 20% ($>20\%$).

Explored Datasets

Dataset	Subjects	Series/Images	Data Types	Supporting Data
Duke-Breast-Cancer-MRI	922	5161/773888	MRI, Segmentation	Clinical, Genomics, Image Analyses
TCGA-BRCA	139	1877/230167	MRI, Mammogram, Pathology	Clinical, Genomics, Image Analyses
CPTAC-BRCA	134	?/642	Pathology	Clinical, Genomics, Proteomics

Duke BC Dataset

[Saha, A., Harowicz, M.R., Grimm, L.J., Kim, C.E., Ghate, S.V., Walsh, R. and Mazurowski, M.A., 2018. A machine learning approach to radiogenomics of breast cancer: a study of 922 subjects and 529 DCE-MRI features. British journal of cancer, 119\(4\), pp.508-516.](#)

Dataset Phenotypes Distribution.

Manufacturer	Model	Cases
GE Medical Systems	Optima MR450z	98
	Signa Excite	10
	Signa HDx	272
	Signa HDxt	248
Siemens	Avanto	179
	Skyra	57
	Trio	1
	Trio-trim	57

Dataset - Annotation Schema

- 772439 images (slices) distributed by 922 patients (average: 838 images per patient).
- Disk storage space of approximately 342 gigabytes, with each DICOM image averaging 443 kilobytes.
- Square Images that varies between 320x320 pixels (33 cases), 448x448 pixels (261 cases), and 512x512 pixels (628 cases).
- Minimum number of slices in which a tumor is identified / detected in a patient case is 2 slices and maximum number is 131 slices.
- *A limitation, only the largest pathological lesion (tumor) was annotated for each patient case.*

Detection of BC Pathological Lesions

Developed Method Workflow

Preprocessing step

Preprocessing step: Selection of slices

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code: Application of the funneling function. As the result of the funneling function is a real number, the value must be converted to an integer. We do so by rounding the value up (ceiling).

```

1: function CALCNUMOFSLICES_TOREMOVE(
    total_number_of_slices_with_tumor
    , total_number_of_slices
    )
2:
3:   Real funnel_result := funneling_function(total_number_of_slices_with_tumor)
4:
5:   return (Integer) total_number_of_slices - ceil(funnel_result)
6: end function
  
```

Algorithm 2 Pseudo-code: Based on the total number of slices, this algorithm calculates the number of slices to remove from each end of the slices with tumor range. When the total number of slices to remove is an odd number, we round down (floor) the number of slices to remove from the beginning of the range and round up (ceil) the number of slices to remove from the end of the range.

```

1: function NUMBEROFSLICES_TOREMOVEFROMEACHSIDE(
    total_number_of_slices_with_tumor
    , total_number_of_slices
    )
2:
3:   Integer number_of_slices_to_remove := CalcNumOfSlicesToRemove(
    total_number_of_slices_with_tumor, total_number_of_slices
    )
4:
5:   Real number_of_slices_to_remove_on_each_side := num_of_slices_to_remove / 2
6:
7:   return (Tuple<Integer, Integer> (
    floor(number_of_slices_to_remove_on_each_side),
    ceil(number_of_slices_to_remove_on_each_side)
    )
    )
8: end function
  
```


Training step

Pre-processed images

- Christian Szegedy, Vincent Vanhoucke, Sergey Ioffe, Jon Shlens, Zbigniew Wojna. Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2016, pp. 2818-2826.
- Ren, S., He, K., Girshick, R., & Sun, J. (2015). Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1506.01497>.
- He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., & Sun, J. (2015). Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. <http://image-net.org/challenges/LSVRC/2015/>

Evaluation step

Patient wise

Metrics are calculated for each patient group of images

Limited by dataset annotations

It is only possible to measure false negatives and true positives

Metrics used

SoftMax score
Accuracy
IoU

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{A1 \cap A2}{A1 \cup A2}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{All correct detections}}{\text{All subjects}} = \frac{\text{TP} + \cancel{\text{TN}}}{\text{TP} + \cancel{\text{FP}} + \cancel{\text{FN}} + \cancel{\text{TN}}}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Detected tumors}}{\text{All subjects with tumor}} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

(Accuracy)

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Detected tumors}}{\text{Correct and incorrect tumor detections}} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \cancel{\text{FP}}} = 1$$

Preliminary Experiments

Cluster B (Vision at VISTA Lab)		
CPU	<i>Designation</i>	Dual AMD Rome 7742
	<i>Cores</i>	128
System memory		1TB
GPUs	<i>Designation</i>	NVIDIA A100 Tensor Core GPU
	<i>N. of GPUs</i>	4
	<i>Cores</i>	6912 (total 27648)
	<i>Memory</i>	40GB (total 160GB)

Model Designatio	Slice selection method	Image Count	
		Train set	Test set
A	All slices with tumor	77963	189% of Model A Same test set with 5031 images
B	Funneling method described in Pre- processing section	41317	53% of Model B

Slice selection specifications

Preliminary Experiments

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Slice selection specifications

METRIC	Model A	Model B	Diff
Train time (hours)	56.653	29.337	27.316
True Positives cases	53	54	1
False Negatives cases	3	2	1
False Negative slices	2611	2212	399
Accuracy	0.946	0.964	0.018
Average IoU	0.246	0.316	0.070
Average Score	0.488	0.591	0.103
Average Max IoU	0.596	0.694	0.098
Average Score @ Max IoU	0.816	0.913	0.097

Cross Validation process

Total number of images per fold depends on the number of slices of each patient.

Remainder 2 patient are always on the training set.

Cross Validation Results

METRIC		FOLD										AVERAGE	STD DEV
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
False Negatives		3	4	2	6	3	5	6	8	5	9	5.10	2.23
Accuracy (%)		96.74	95.65	97.83	93.48	96.74	94.57	93.48	91.30	94.57	90.22	94.46	2.43
Average IoU (%)	all	31.22	28.00	27.89	29.31	27.67	28.08	28.14	27.93	27.96	23.29	27.95	1.96
	IoU > 0	32.27	29.27	28.51	31.36	28.60	29.69	30.11	30.59	29.57	25.81	29.58	1.77
Average Score (%)	all	57.65	52.20	53.07	52.56	55.44	54.18	50.60	54.76	51.24	44.95	52.66	3.42
	IoU > 0	59.16	54.57	54.04	56.06	57.26	57.25	54.06	59.61	54.05	49.34	55.54	3.01
Average Max IoU (%)	all	69.02	63.69	66.47	65.42	64.44	66.35	65.87	62.82	66.51	61.85	65.25	2.09
	IoU > 0	71.34	66.59	67.95	69.99	66.61	70.17	70.47	68.80	70.34	68.56	69.08	1.65
Average Score @ Max IoU (%)	all	87.15	84.07	86.18	85.58	86.39	85.23	83.71	79.99	82.33	81.49	84.21	2.34
	IoU > 0	90.08	87.89	88.09	91.56	89.30	90.12	89.55	87.61	87.06	90.32	89.16	1.44

Detection Examples

LEFT BREAST:

BI-RADS 6

*Extensive **proliferative** lesion, including the biopsied nodule, in the **mid transition of the upper quadrants**/11 hours, 6 cm from the nipple, extending to the region of upper and internal tumourectomy, and aspect of focal intra ductal segmental uptake with **small suspicious peri ductal nodules to the nipple.***

RIGHT BREAST:

BI-RADS 4

*Small non-specific **retroareolar nodule** at right, deserving a 2nd look ultrasound and ultrasound-guided microbiopsy.*

BI-RADS 4:

Suspicious abnormality – Biopsy should be considered

BI-RADS 6:

Known biopsy-proven malignancy – Appropriate action should be taken

Diagnosis of BC phenotypes

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

A 3D-CNN approach for the diagnosis of Luminal-A (LA) breast cancer, a subtype characterized by positive hormone receptor expression and negative HER2 expression.

A binary classification strategy was followed to distinguish between LA and non-LA phenotypes by analyzing volumetric (3D) patients' images (cases).

The developed 3D CNN classification model can take into account the 3D structure of the breast tissue and capture more detailed information about the tumor's microenvironment, leading to better accuracy and higher sensitivity in diagnosis

It is explored specific morphological characteristics to improve the diagnostic accuracy and efficacy of the LA phenotype.

In experimental settings, we achieved an AUC score of 0.9786 and an F_1 -score of 0.9502.

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

```
Data:  $v \leftarrow$  MRI volume
Result:  $v \leftarrow$  Preprocessed volume
 $min \leftarrow -1000$ ;
 $max \leftarrow 400$ ;
 $depth\_factor \leftarrow 1/(v.depth/64)$ ;
 $width\_factor \leftarrow 1/(v.width/128)$ ;
 $height\_factor \leftarrow 1/(v.height/128)$ ;
for  $i \leftarrow$  volume indexes do
  if  $v[i] < min$  then
    |  $v[i] \leftarrow min$ 
  else
    | if  $v[i] > max$  then
      | |  $v[i] \leftarrow max$ 
    | end
  end
end
end
for  $i \leftarrow$  volume indexes do
  |  $v[i] \leftarrow (v[i] - min)/(max - min)$ 
end
end
 $v \leftarrow scale(v, (depth\_factor, width\_factor, height\_factor))$ 
```

Preprocessing: to build a 64-slice volume with 128x128 resolution, including normalization and zoom operations.

2D sample slices from the volume representing the tumor, after preprocessing.

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

Architecture of the 3D CNN model for Luminal A phenotype classification in tumor volumes. The model consists of four groups of convolutional layers, max pooling, and batch normalization. The features extracted are then subjected to global average pooling to flatten to a 1D tensor and fed into a dense layer with 512 units, followed by a dropout rate of 0.3 and a final dense layer outputting the probability of the tumor volume belonging to the LA phenotype.

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

Metrics / Achieved Results

Metric	Formula	Metric	Zhu et al. [1]	Yin et al. [2]	Saha et al. [3]	2D	3D
Accuracy	$\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$	Accuracy	NA	0.77	NA	0.6777	0.9329
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$	Precision	NA	NA	NA	0.6891	0.9677
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$	Recall	NA	0.67	NA	0.9693	0.9333
F ₁ -Score	$\frac{2*(precision*recall)}{(precision+recall)}$	AUC	0.65	0.82 ± 0.08	0.697 ± 0.05	0.5003	0.9786
		F ₁ -Score	NA	NA	NA	0.8055	0.9502

1. Zhu, Z.; Albadawy, E.; Saha, A.; Zhang, J.; Harowicz, M.R.; Mazurowski, M.A. **Deep learning for identifying radiogenomic associations in breast cancer.** *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 2019, 109, 85–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COMPBIOMED.2019.04.018>.
2. Yin, H.; Bai, L.; Jia, H.; Lin, G. **Noninvasive assessment of breast cancer molecular subtypes on multiparametric MRI using convolutional neural network with transfer learning.** *Thoracic cancer* 2022, 13, 3183–3191. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1759-7714.673>.
3. Saha, A.; Harowicz, M.R.; Grimm, L.J.; et al. **A machine learning approach to radiogenomics of breast cancer: a study of 922 subjects and 529 DCE-MRI features.** *British Journal of Cancer* 2018, 119, 508. <https://doi.org/10.1038/S41416-018-0185-8>.

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

Conclusions and Future Work

- A new MRI-based 3D-CNN model to classify the *Luminal-A breast cancer phenotype*.
- The developed model achieved an AUC of 0.9786, outperforming all other methods we used as a basis of comparison for this study.
- It is demonstrated again that using class weights during training may be an effective technique in overcoming the issue of unbalanced data.
- *Further investigations are needed to adapt our approach to addressing the diagnosis of remaining phenotypes (Luminal-B, HER2-enriched, and Triple-negative)*

Phenotyping “Luminal-A” BC in MRI. A 3D-CNN approach

Acknowledgments

- We would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to the Vista_Lab research unit, University of Évora, Portugal for providing us access to the [“Vision cluster”](#).
- The high-performance computing capabilities of the [Vision cluster](#) allowed us to reduce the training time of our models, enabling us to efficiently process and analyze the large amount of data used in this study.

Many thanks